

THE IMPORTANCE OF LARGE BUSINESS IN SHAPING THE GREEN ECONOMY

Asliddin Umaraliyev Fakhritdin Ogli

Tashkent institute of chemical technology, faculty of management
and professional education

umaraliyev97@mail.ru

Abstract: While small businesses play a crucial role in promoting sustainability, the influence of large corporations on the green economy cannot be overstated. This article explores the role of large businesses in driving sustainability, highlighting their unique capabilities and responsibilities in shaping a greener future.

Key words: Green economy, considerable business in green economy, environmental sustainability, importance of considerable business in green economy, support of green economy.

INTRODUCTION

Big companies are essential to the advancement of the green economy. Large companies may undertake sustainability efforts on a massive scale and reach a great number of suppliers and consumers thanks to their scale, resources, and influence. Big companies can afford to invest in renewable energy sources including hydroelectric, wind, and solar energy. Large firms can lessen their carbon footprint and help create a more sustainable energy system by switching to renewable energy sources and making investments in sustainable infrastructure. As a result, they can drastically lessen their environmental impact and promote progress in a variety of industries. The capacity of huge companies to invest in innovation is one of their main benefits. They can devote funds to research and development, which will result in the development of cutting-edge green practices and technologies. These developments advance sustainable solutions more broadly in addition to being advantageous to the business. Global supply chains are a feature of large organizations as well. They can encourage the adoption of environmentally friendly practices at every stage of the supply chain and foster environmental stewardship by establishing sustainability criteria for their suppliers.

METHODS AND ANALYSIS

Prominent companies frequently establish the benchmark for industry procedures. By making sustainability a top priority in their business operations, they can persuade colleagues and rivals to do the same, which will result in the sector as a whole adopting green practices widely. Many large corporations have robust Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) programs that focus on environmental

sustainability. These initiatives go beyond regulatory compliance and demonstrate a commitment to making a positive impact on the environment and society. To advance sustainability initiatives, big firms can work with other institutions such as governments, non-profits, and small and medium-sized enterprises. By utilizing each partner's unique skills, these alliances have the potential to have a bigger impact than any one organization could on its own. Big businesses can also reduce their environmental impact by putting circular economy techniques like product recycling and waste reduction into practice. To advance sustainability initiatives, big firms can work with other institutions such as governments, non-profits, and small and medium-sized enterprises. By utilizing each partner's unique skills, these alliances have the potential to have a bigger impact than any one organization could on its own. Big businesses can also reduce their environmental impact by putting circular economy techniques like product recycling and waste reduction into practice. Big businesses may help create a more sustainable economy by putting effective waste management systems in place and developing products with recycling in mind. Through marketing and advertising initiatives, large enterprises can also reach a large audience. Large enterprises have the power to shape customer behavior and promote more sustainable choices by bringing attention to environmental challenges and encouraging sustainable lifestyles. Large corporations can also spur innovation and ongoing sustainability development by establishing challenging objectives, tracking their success, and looking for cutting-edge methods and technology that lessen their environmental effect. Large corporations and individual entrepreneurs are key to this paradigm change, having a vital and diverse role in the shift to an ecologically conscious and sustainable economy. At this stage, accomplishing the ensuing objectives will work as a useful roadmap for companies to follow in order to make informed decisions in the contemporary worldwide market.

- Assessment of the impact of large businesses and private enterprises on environmental sustainability.
- Analysis of the role of considerable business in the development of green innovations and technologies.
- Assess policy frameworks that support and encourage sustainable practices among considerable businesses and private enterprises.
- Explore case studies of successful businesses and their contribution to the green economy.
- Analysis of the organization of activities and the scope of influence of politicians, business owners and stakeholders on increasing the role of small business activities in the green economy.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

This is why large business is the main topic of this article. Large enterprises have financial opportunities to invest in research, development and the introduction of green technologies and practices. Their investments can stimulate innovation and accelerate the transition to a low-carbon economy, another main aspects of large companies in developing the benefits of green economy is emission reduction. Large corporations are often among the largest emitters of greenhouse gases. By achieving ambitious austerity goals and implementing climate-friendly practices, they can have a significant impact on global emissions and contribute to efforts to mitigate climate change. They invest in research and development, leading to technological advancements that benefit the entire economy. Large businesses also invest in infrastructure projects, improving efficiency and productivity. They play a significant role in international trade, promoting economic integration and access to new markets. Large businesses contribute a substantial amount of tax revenue, supporting public services and infrastructure. They have extensive supply chains, benefiting small and medium-sized enterprises.

CONCLUSION. All in all, enhancing the role of large businesses in the green economy is a collaborative effort that requires supportive policies, proactive actions by business owners, and community and industry stakeholders requires participation. If these groups work together, they can make meaningful progress toward a more sustainable future.

REFERENCES

1. Vaxabov A.V., Xajibakiyev Sh.X., Tashmatov Sh.A., Butaboyev M.T.. Yashil iqtisodiyot. Darslik. T.: Universitet, 2020.
2. "Ministry of Economic Development and Poverty Alleviation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, World Bank, Regional Ecological Center of Central Asia, 2022.
3. Yashil iqtisodiyot darslik /A.B.Вахабов, Ш.Х.Хажикакиев – Тошкент.: “Universitet”, 2020.
4. Dusmatov B.O., Fazilov V.A. INNOVATIVE APPROACHES TO MANAGING THE DEVELOPMENT OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES.
5. <https://corporate.enelx.com/en/question-and-answers/what-is-green-economy#:~:text=The%20definition%20of%20green%20economy,fosters%20social%20and%20environmental%20sustainability.>
6. <https://www.unep.org/regions/asia-and-pacific/regional-initiatives/supporting-resource-efficiency/green-economy.>
7. Порфирьев Б.П., "Зеленая" экономика: реалии, перспективы и пределы роста. 2013. - М.: Карнеги.